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Engineering beautification of urban areas and disclosure of general concepts.

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Abstract: Elements of knowledge, skills and competence formation on the issues of engineering beautification of urban areas and disclosure of general concepts, basic laws in the development of nature, its interaction and interaction with society in the conditions of scientific, technical and social development. methods and principles of organization are considered by summarizing and analyzing.

Key words: engineering, city, landscaping, construction, planning, preparation.

INTRODUCTION

Only as a result of in-depth analysis of natural disasters, production accidents and environmental situations that are characteristic for the region of Uzbekistan (the cause of each situation, its strength, scope of influence, consequences for people, environment study) the most convenient measures against them are determined, so that as a result it is possible to reduce the scale of both material and moral losses in any emergency situations. [1] Creating and implementing an optimal plan of cities requires the search for ways to use some spare areas that have not been used in the existing urban area. For this purpose, it is of practical importance to develop the places considered "inconvenient" based on the requirements of civil protection and urban planning. Swamps, ravines, low-lying areas and others are among such "unfavorable" places. [2]

METHOD OF RESEARCH

In the process of planning for the implementation of creative work in places, residential and historical monument buildings, green areas, ancient tree groves and surrounding valuable areas in the city area should be integrated (in the master plan and vertical cut) to complete the solution of civil protection. Ensuring compliance is the main

goal of engineering training in the urban area. In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks must be solved:

a) measures to adapt the place to construction - determination of measures (lowering the level of underground water, protecting the area from flooding, landslides and ravines, establishing irrigation of green fields, floods, earthquakes , prevention of sandblasting);

b) elimination of factors that do not meet construction requirements in the regions, i.e. ensuring the natural flow of snow and rainwater;

c) prevention of washing and scouring of the shores by greening the surroundings of rivers, streams and lakes;

g) irrigating green areas in the city, draining snow, rain and waste water on a natural slope, not allowing swamps to form;

The main tasks of vertical planning of urban areas are:

1) organization of surface (atmospheric) water flow by providing the flow direction to the city underground drainage network along the slopes and surface of the building and along the city streets;

2) providing convenient and safe movement of city vehicles and pedestrians by providing acceptable longitudinal slopes to city streets and roads;

3) creating areas for the construction of buildings and structures by changing and adapting the relief to the requirements of the development of blocks, microdistricts and individual buildings and structures;

4) creating the most favorable terrain for laying urban underground communications;

5) solving special problems related to the terrain and its vertical location during the construction of unique objects (groups of buildings, stadium, airfield). [3]

In the vertical planning of the territories of microdistricts and residential areas, the following is carried out:

- creation of areas in accordance with the development project, taking into account the

configuration, purpose and overall compositional solution for planning and development of the buildings and structures;

- provision of convenient longitudinal and transverse slopes for the safe movement of vehicles and pedestrians on highways, sidewalks, footpaths and roads, in areas of various purposes;

- a device for collecting and removing surface rain and melt water outside the neighborhoods or microdistricts.

In vertical planning, it is very important to preserve the vegetation layer of the land and the existing green areas. [4]

Figure 1. Landscaping network.¹

RESEARCH RESULTS

In addition, it is necessary to provide the level of the surface of the land where the city will be built with a standard (>0.015) slope, to ensure that the top layer of the soil is not washed away and its surface is not exposed to

wind erosion. In the implementation of such engineering measures, great importance is also attached to the improvement and landscaping of the site. [5], [6]

One of the main tasks of the engineering measures to reduce the underground water level is to ensure the discharge of snow, rain and wastewater through the water collector to the water treatment basins outside the

¹ <https://triptonkosti.ru/1-foto/luchshaya-3d-karta-80-foto.html>

city. In order not to raise the underground water level, the extent and volume of earthworks determined on the basis of the vertical planning method will depend on economic efficiency. For this reason, it is advisable to use a depth of close distance when removing the excavated soil. When performing such works, sometimes the initial shape of the relief can be completely changed. An example of this can be the construction of dams to protect against flooding, the engineering activities carried out in the burial and leveling of ravines. [7], [8]

The following architectural, planning, engineering and technical problems are solved in the development of measures for the engineering improvement of urban areas:

- engineering training;
- engineering equipment;
- beautification and landscaping;
- sanitary cleaning;
- environmental protection and improvement.

The composition, sequence and content of the complex of engineering activities depends on natural environmental factors, the level of anthropogenic and man-made destruction of the area, the size of the object and its functional purpose. [9] [10]

One of the most important measures for the engineering development of cities is the engineering preparation of areas.

In order to achieve the most correct functional-planning and economic solution, issues of engineering preparation of territories should be connected with the overall compositional and architectural planning solution of the urban area.

Planning projects for cities and other settlements include: - development of a scheme of planning restrictions (inclusion of unfavorable areas for construction due to

flooding with groundwater, water basin pollution, etc.);

- development of a system of measures for engineering preparation of the territory, including the basis of vertical planning;

- proposals for the organization of surface water drainage, the fight against flooding of a wide area in the city, ravines and other unfavorable events;

- general proposals regarding the character of beautification of the city, formation of its system of green areas, construction of embankments and bridges;

- environmental protection measures.

Engineering preparation of the territory, beautification and environmental protection measures are developed in close connection with architectural and planning solutions, designed transport system, engineering supply (water supply, sewage, energy supply). developed. urban area.

So an architect should have enough knowledge of engineering.

CONCLUSIONS

The engineering activities carried out at the initial stage of the city building process are taken into account. Among them are the climatic conditions of the place, the hydro-geological condition of the land, the connections related to the condition of the terrain, etc.

- urban development and city planning - in which the condition of the land is taken into account when dividing the city into regions depending on the characteristics of the city.

- urban engineering beautification and greening, engineering constructions and communications, city streets and roads - issues of ensuring the reliability of the elements of the municipal character of this city are considered.

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